

A Perfect Match: Converging and Automating Privacy & Security Impact Assessment On-the-Fly

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Abstract: As the upsurge of information and communication technologies has become the foundation of all modern application domains, fueled by the unprecedented amount of data being processed and exchanged, besides security concerns, there are also pressing privacy considerations that come into play. Compounding this issue, there is currently a documented gap between the cybersecurity and privacy risk assessment (RA) avenues, which are treated as distinct management processes and capitalise on rather rigid and make-like approaches. In this paper, we aim to combine the best of both worlds by proposing the APSIA methodology, which stands for Automated Privacy & Security Impact Assessment. APSIA is powered by the use of interdependency graph models and data processing flows used to create a digital reflection of the cyber-physical environment of an organisation. Along with this model, we present a novel and extensible privacy risk scoring system for quantifying the privacy impact triggered by the identified vulnerabilities of the ICT infrastructure of an organisation. We provide a prototype implementation and demonstrate its applicability and efficacy through a specific case study in the context of a heavily regulated sector (i.e., assistive healthcare domain) where strict security and privacy considerations are not only expected but mandated so as to better showcase the beneficial characteristics of APSIA. Our approach can complement any existing security-based RA tool and provide the means to conduct an *enhanced*, *dynamic* and *generic* assessment as an integral part of an iterative and unified risk assessment process on-the-fly. Based on our findings, we posit open issues and challenges, and discuss possible ways to address them, so that such holistic security and privacy mechanisms can reach their full potential towards solving this conundrum.

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1. Introduction

Six decades since the start of the computer revolution, four decades since the invention of the micro-processor, and two decades into the rise of the modern Internet, all of the technology required to transform industries through software has finally matured and can be widely delivered at a global scale. Moreover, with the advent of the Internet of Things (IoT), the world just begun reaping the benefits of this evolution. However, this evolution brings several new challenges (or makes existing unsolved challenges urgent to be tackled) with *security*, *interoperability*, *integrability*, and *composability* being some of the major concerns at both logical extremes of a network. Currently, such challenges are addressed by next-generation approaches including model-based standards, ontology, Business Process Model Life-Cycle Management (BPM LCM), context of business process, and a host of other transport protocols [1–3].

Security, on the other hand, is of paramount importance and is addressed by conducting risk management as a first step. According to the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), in the face of an increasing attack landscape (Figure 1), it is

38 imperative to ensure the correct and safe operation of all safety-critical business processes
39 because, by their very nature, the internal physical and cyber (data and computing)
40 assets - of an ecosystem or application domain - may not always be in trusted custody.
41 Towards this direction, organizations must perform risk management so that they can
42 identify and assess risks in order to keep them at acceptable levels. *It serves as the*
43 *foundation on which organizations can start building a well-rounded cybersecurity strategy.*

44 In this context, the most fundamental component of risk management is risk as-
45 sessment. Risk assessment targets the identification of threats and of respective risk
46 levels, thus, allowing for the overall risk management to keep cybersecurity risks under
47 an acceptable threshold [4]. According to the Risk Management Framework (RMF)
48 proposed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), risk assessment
49 can be performed in three tiers: the organizational; business process; and Information
50 Systems tier [3]. In the era where *“service is everything and everything is a service”*, this risk
51 compartmentalization enables the emerging trend of the intelligent edge computing and
52 the backend information service provider to operate in tandem, so as to provide flexible
53 design choices that best meet business and operational goals. However, as the upsurge
54 of such information and communication technologies has become the nervous system
55 of all modern economies, fueled by the unprecedented amount of personal data being
56 processed and exchanged [5], besides security concerns, there are also pressing privacy
57 considerations that come into play and need to be taken into consideration.

58 The rising number of privacy related incidents has, therefore, mandated much
59 stricter data protection and privacy principles, especially in sectors where massive
60 amounts of sensitive data are processed; i.e., such as healthcare, Industrial IoT, etc. [6–8].
61 Privacy refers to the protection of personal data or Personally Identifiable Information
62 (PII) and is regarded as a human right in the digital age [9]. Privacy is challenging
63 not only because it is an all-encompassing concept that helps to safeguard important
64 values, such as human autonomy and dignity, but also because there is a wide spectrum
65 of threats against it, and at the same time, the means for achieving it can vary [10,11].
66 Towards this direction, privacy risk management approaches have emerged in order
67 to identify and mitigate privacy risks raised during data processing activities. The
68 paramount importance of privacy preservation, along with the establishment of the
69 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that governs the European territory, has
70 rendered the privacy risk assessment a rapidly changing field, due to notable standard-
71 isation actions and legal establishments. However, *a common language and a practical*
72 *methodology that is flexible enough to address diverse privacy needs is still missing* [10], while
73 the community has identified the need for further research towards the implementation
74 of tools to support Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) conduction [12].

75 Even though there are several frameworks that set the principles for the conduction
76 of privacy risk assessment, PIA remains a challenging and maze-like process mainly
77 due to the multiple aspects that an assessor needs to consider; sometimes by having
78 limited view to the details of the processing activities of interest and the supporting
79 assets of the ICT infrastructure. In this line of research, intensive research efforts have
80 converged to the proposal of a wide gamut of PIA complementary tools: While they can
81 prove valuable during the assessment process, it appears that most of them perform
82 the assessment without considering the cybersecurity status of the ICT infrastructure.
83 This is rather contradictory considering the NIST proposed guidelines [10], according
84 to which, the data protection lies in the intersection of the cybersecurity and privacy
85 risks. Therefore, the lack of sufficient tools and methodologies that can offer the PIA
86 a level of automation [12], so that risk impact assessment can be extracted in a timely
87 manner, but most importantly the lack of proper metrics that can steer the decisions of
88 the assessor in identifying, prioritising, anticipating and, finally, mitigating the risks,
89 could raise questions on the effectiveness of the tools and the thoroughness of the
90 assessments. Indeed, the diversity and complexity of proposed privacy properties makes
91 an informed choice of metrics rather challenging [13] and sets the challenge ahead on

Figure 1. Potential cyber-attack methods, targets and effects

92 how to efficiently converge the usually contradicting security and privacy requirements,
93 of a business ecosystem, towards a better risk assessment and estimation.

94 **Contributions:** We meet these challenges with APSIA; a novel systematic approach
95 towards assessing the privacy impact levels of organisations while also considering
96 their cybersecurity status and threat landscape, as those are formed by the chains of
97 interdependent ICT assets used to realise the data processing. APSIA is capable not
98 only to support and complement PIA procedures, but also to enhance their assessments
99 with dynamic asset inventory and vulnerability discovery techniques, extending beyond
100 the initial setup and deployment of a business ecosystem to also consider the entire
101 operational life-cycle of an organization. More specifically, APSIA: (i) is generic and
102 applicable to any type of business ecosystem or application domain, (ii) leverages
103 a novel and extensible privacy risk scoring system for quantifying the privacy risks
104 triggered by the identified vulnerabilities of the ICT infrastructure of an organisation,
105 (iii) provides a dynamic model for mapping core GDPR entities and requirements with
106 tangible (e.g. databases, servers) and intangible assets (e.g. data records, PII) of the ICT
107 infrastructures, so that to enable the risk assessors to effectively define data processing
108 activities, and (iv) enables the risk assessor to keep track of all the needed information
109 and assess the degree of compliance of the organisation including in the assessment
110 the existence of risk mitigation actions. We provide a prototype implementation of
111 APSIA and demonstrate its applicability and efficacy through a specific case study in
112 a healthcare setting. While one could argue that APSIA is limited only to the GDPR-
113 related privacy considerations, the core methodology is generic enough to facilitate any
114 ecosystem with “privacy-by-design” properties. Since such properties are independent
115 of the system or the application domain itself, putting forth the methodology to be able
116 to precisely model them in the presence of strong adversaries is a prerequisite for any
117 legal framework. Overall, our approach can complement any existing security-based
118 risk assessment tool, closing the existing gap and enhancing the privacy posture of all
119 involved actors against powerful adversaries.

120 The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we offer an overview of
121 the related endeavors and frameworks in the PIA field. Section 3 presents the APSIA
122 methodology and elaborates on the systematic approach of regulating and conducting
123 the cybersecurity and privacy risk assessment. We then provide a detailed description
124 of the APSIA’s workflow of actions and internal components (Section 4), followed by
125 a showcase of its mode of operation in a healthcare environment (Section 5). Section
126 6 puts forth open issues and challenges that still need to be considered towards even
127 more holistic risk assessment services capable of capturing the intricacies of emerging
128 “Systems-of-Systems” settings. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

129 2. The Emergence of Privacy Impact Assessment

130 PIA is a risk management approach which aims at the evaluation of potential effects
131 that systems may have on privacy, due to processing actions on personal data [11].
132 Via this systematic approach, organisations can anticipate the risks of their initiatives

133 during their life-cycle, starting from the design phase - enabling a “privacy-by-design”
134 approach - but also during their operational life-cycle by performing iterative assessment.
135 Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) and standardisation bodies have established legal
136 frameworks and guidelines which mandate the conduction of PIA. In an effort to gain
137 the European citizens’ trust for digital services, the General Data Protection Regulation
138 (GDPR) refers to the obligation of the data controller to conduct an impact assessment
139 and to document it prior to starting the intended data processing (Art. 35). The Inter-
140 national Organization for Standardization (ISO) released a PIA guidelines standard,
141 namely ISO/IEC 29134:2017, for standardising the PIA per se, and the reporting process
142 and format [14].

143 In what follows, we provide an overview of relevant risk assessment standards
144 and PIA tools in order highlight their benefits but also challenges in comparison to
145 APSIA. The intuition is to showcase that besides the NIST privacy framework [10], the
146 aforementioned privacy concerns are highly overlooked in today’s standards while
147 a common quantification formula for calculating the privacy risks together with the
148 existing cybersecurity metrics is still an open and challenging task.

149 2.1. Methodologies, Standards and GDPR Guidelines

150 There are several privacy data protection standards, such as BS 10012:2017 [15], the
151 ISO/IEC 29151:2017 [16] and the ISO/IEC 27018:2014 [17], where the Privacy Impact As-
152 sessment (PIA) included as a mandatory step towards conducting cyber risk assessment.
153 Unfortunately, there is no explicit methodology that performs a PIA consolidated with
154 a risk assessment process. The vast majority treats the PIA independently of the cyber
155 risk assessment [18,19], even though according to the NIST privacy framework [10] the
156 data protection lies in the intersection between the cyber security and privacy risks. In
157 addition, there is a documented gap for automated tools that can support the conduction
158 of a PIA [4]. A comprehensive guidance for carrying out a PIA presented in ISO/IEC
159 29134:2017 [20], however, it solely describes the the basic concepts for the impact analysis
160 while the provided information for the risk assessor is inadequate [19]. Moreover, several
161 privacy metrics have been documented in the literature by now, however these generally
162 utilise criteria of privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), such as the the quantification
163 of leaked information or the number of indistinguishable users, instead of the privacy
164 impact [21]. More recently, the NIST proposed a privacy framework in the form of a
165 solid documentation and a methodology to manage the privacy risks of an organization
166 by prioritizing privacy protection activities through enterprise risk management [10].

167 The GDPR commands controllers to perform a risk oriented approach for the
168 personal data, the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) [22]. However, GDPR
169 does not dictate a special assessment method, while at the same time mandates a good
170 overview of the PIIs, since any inappropriate management of PIIs can possibly violate
171 the GDPR [23]. Such an overview is a challenging task especially for complex systems
172 designed before the GDPR era. To handle this issue, it is necessary to identify and
173 document all the activities related to processing the PIIs [23].

174 Numerous national regulators have circulated guidelines for DPIA, among them are
175 the French CNIL [24], the British ICO [22] and Canada’s Privacy Act [25]. Such guides has
176 been amended to support DPIAs and to provide comprehensive guidelines about their
177 regulatory requirements and processes. These guidelines follow different approaches
178 and propose diverse steps for conducting a PIA, while are abstract or imprecise, making
179 difficult to conduct such methodologies [26]. Thus, the adoption of a single methodology
180 becomes a difficult task for an organisation and this results to inadequate support for
181 conducting a PIA [4]. A more recent research work, reviewed the most known DPIA
182 methods based on seventeen questions derived from the literature in order to highlight
183 the absence of completeness among DPIA methods [4]. While there are differences in
184 the aforementioned approaches, they are equally suitable for conducting a DPIA and
185 produce largely similar results.

186 2.2. *Understanding the Differences between PIAs and the GDPR's DPIAs*

187 In addition to the aforementioned regulatory efforts, amendments on the DPIA
188 processes has also been proposed from the academia. These efforts include making the
189 DPIA process more systematic and structured by using formal modeling techniques for
190 privacy threats [19]. LINDDUN is a privacy threat analysis framework that can support
191 analysts in systematically eliciting and mitigating privacy threats and consists of six
192 main steps [27]. The acronym stands for Linkability, Identifiability, Non-repudiation,
193 Detectability, Disclosure of information, Unawareness and Non-compliance. LINDDUN
194 and the CNIL method [28] have common principles. LINDDUN, however, has the func-
195 tionality to visualise data flow diagrams and privacy threat tree patterns [29] compared
196 to the CNIL. However, LINDDUN is missing assessment steps from a legal perspective
197 and also is not integrated with a risk assessment process [23]. The work in [30] presents a
198 methodology, firstly introduced in [26], to reinforce the privacy enhancement of a system
199 design model, since there is a lack of a common methodology concerning the design of
200 IT systems [26]. More precisely, a systematic model-based cost estimation methodology
201 is proposed that takes into consideration a range of privacy controls, including privacy-
202 design strategies, patterns, and PETs as well as the interrelations and dependencies
203 among them. More recently, the authors in [31] propose a detailed methodology for
204 identifying and quantifying data privacy risks, while the risk values are calculated at
205 two different levels for helping the senior management and the operational personnel
206 to assess and mitigate privacy risks. In addition, the work in [19] present a systematic
207 privacy-related information security risk assessment (pISRA) model, which combines
208 both a privacy impact analysis and a risk assessment. In [32], the authors present an
209 empirically evaluated privacy risk assessment framework, the DPIA Data Wheel. This
210 framework considers the contextual integrity that practitioners can use to take decision
211 around the privacy risks of Cyber Physical Systems (CPS). Unfortunately, most of the
212 research efforts do not implement their proposed method/model.

213 2.3. *The Current landscape in PIA Frameworks & Tools*

214 When it comes to existing PIA tools, these mainly fall under the efforts that have
215 been conducted by various standardization bodies which have resulted to the following
216 schemes: the ENISA tool [33], the GS1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool [34], the SPIA Tool [35] and
217 the CNIL tool [36]. Most tools on the market have a rather narrow scope of application,
218 with a single use case being the norm. There exist a considerable number of tools
219 supporting the documentation of data processing practices, the formulation of consent
220 templates, or the documentation of privacy and data protection policies. However, the
221 cybersecurity status of the organisation in which the impact analysis is performed is
222 largely neglected.

223 **ENISA tool:** ENISA offers an online privacy tool for evaluating the risk level of the
224 personal data processing operations [33]. This tool builds on existing works [28,37,38] in
225 the field and aims to provide guidance to SMEs and support data controllers/processors.
226 The adopted approach consists of six steps towards offering a simplified approach and
227 guide the SMEs to a data processing operation and assist them evaluate the privacy-
228 related security risks. Through the proposed steps, the assessor defines the context of
229 the processing operation and determines manually how the fundamental rights and
230 freedoms of the individuals could be harmed from the possible loss of security of the
231 personal data. Four levels of impact are supported ranging from Low to Very High. In
232 addition the assessor manually documents both the external and internal threats of the
233 environment and assess their threat occurrence probability. After the impact evaluation
234 of the personal data processing operation and the corresponding threat probability, the
235 final evaluation of risk is delivered. Based on the result, the tool assists the process of
236 adopting new privacy security measures.

237 **GS1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool:** The GS1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool [34] focuses on EPC/RFID
238 applications in the context of large corporations and small and medium enterprises

(SMEs). The tool assists in the conduction of the assessment of privacy risks of RFID implementations and contributes to the identification of privacy controls to be considered during the development of the applications. The tool is aligned with the European Commission's RFID Recommendations and with EPC Privacy Guidelines. The tool is an MS excel file which assists in the definition of the risk level scores based on the formula $Rik = Impact \times Likelihood - Controls$. The score considers the control effectiveness to determine the residual risk. Through the process the assessor answers specified questions/consideration and can define the arbitrary controls and their effectiveness in the scale of [1-5]. The tool does not focus on identifying technical aspects of the implementations to shed light on privacy risks that can be raised due to actual threat vectors targeting the deployment. In addition, the criteria for scoring are rather generalized and not specific for privacy risks [39], while the assessment is limited to the technology field of EPC/RFID applications.

SPIA Tool: The Security and Privacy Impact Assessment (SPIA) Tool [35] aims to help organisations to conduct PIA, by identify areas of risks and select the suitable strategies and timeframes for the risk mitigation. SPIA focuses on both security and privacy for protecting data with a focus on safeguards and is a tool developed by the University of Pennsylvania. The first version of the tool is an MS excel file, while the second version, SPIA 2.0 Tool shifted to a web-based application. SPIA enables organizations to take probability rankings and threat consequences and automatically score risk into categories of *High, Significant, Moderate and Low* [40]. The calculated risk score is actually the product of probability and consequence, while the level of probability and consequence are entered in the tool manually. Last but not least, the SPIA Tool is also an adaptable and versatile tool that supports additional threats both security and privacy.

CNIL PIA method and tool: The CNIL tool [36] aims to assist data controllers to perform DPIA based on the methodology published by CNIL in [24,28]. According to CNIL's methodology a PIA is based on two main aspects:

- fundamental rights and principles, which are "non-negotiable", mandated by law and which must be respected, regardless of the risk nature.
- management of data subjects' privacy risks, which determines the appropriate technical and organisational controls to protect personal data.

The PIA practitioners need to carry out the following necessary steps:

- Define and document the context of the data processing action under consideration.
- Analysis of controls that can protect fundamental principles.
- Assessment and management of privacy risks related to data.
- Formal documentation and validation of the PIA.

The PIA tool assist the practitioners in fulfilling the above-mentioned steps. The result of the assessment is represented through a heat map, where the risks are positioned based on their criticality and the risk likelihood. CNIL tool supports four levels of severity scales; *Negligible, Limited, Significant, Maximum*. However, defining the processing activities with the engaged actors and data, and the underlined threats, is a manual process which requires considerable effort by the tool user and deep understanding for the current data processing actions of the organisation. As a result, the tool lacks automation that can increase the awareness of the risk assessor, while the cyber security status, i.e., the vulnerabilities of the ICT assets are not reflected in the final scores.

Overall, ENISA's on-line tool [33], consists of six steps for the calculation of the privacy risk. The assessment of risks is the first step towards the adoption of appropriate security measures to protect the personal data. This tool engages the user in a manual process of data entry and does not provide any level of automation. The CNIL's PIA tool [36] considers data controllers that are familiar with the PIA process. This tool lacks automation, in terms of ICT asset inventory and privacy threat and vulnerability detection, that can increase the awareness of the risk assessor, while the resulted risk

		Features							
		Asset interdependencies	Data processing flow visualisation	Automation & Dynamicity	Cyber risk consideration	Mitigation controls	GDPR PIA Support	Automated Privacy impact scoring	Legal Framework
PIA Tools	ENISA Tool	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	GDPR
	GS1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	N/A
	SPIA Tool	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	HIPAA
	CNIL Tool	-	-	✓ ¹	-	✓	✓	-	GDPR
	APSLA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	GDPR

¹ Offers a level of automation but not dynamicity when it comes to ICT asset management and vulnerabilities detection

Table 1: Comparison of tools

292 levels do not consider the cyber security status of the organization. Moreover CNIL's
 293 PIA tool does not use visual representation of the information flows, which is a corner
 294 stone of DPIA.

295 The scoring criteria of SPIA Tool [35] are difficult to be extracted from the available
 296 online sources. According to the tool designers, SPIA is able to conduct both cybersecurity
 297 and privacy assessment. However, considering that the tool is offered in a web
 298 environment, it is not destined to interact with the assessed infrastructure and support
 299 asset inventory and vulnerability detection functionalities. The scoring criteria of S1
 300 EPC/RFID PIA Tool [34] are rather generalized [39]. Moreover, S1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool
 301 is simpler than SPIA Tool, but is incompatible with older computers [39]. Last but not
 302 least, S1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool has not been well-received or widely-used and the user
 303 community has identified the absence of technology-specific guidance regarding both
 304 risks and controls [41]. In addition, it has to be noted that S1 EPC/RFID PIA Tool is
 305 a domain specific tool that cannot be considered usable to other application domains.
 306 Table 1 offers an overview of the key characteristics of the aforementioned tools and
 307 highlights the additional aspects that makes APSIA to excel.

308 In this context, as aforementioned, APSIA aims to bridge the gap between the cyber-
 309 and privacy-risk assessment, which are treated as distinct management processes [18,
 310 19]. It tackles one of the current field's shortfalls, which is the lack of a risk scoring
 311 system that adequately considers the context and the primary goal, i.e., the privacy
 312 preservation, of the environment for identified vulnerabilities, as this can lead the
 313 organisations to improperly prioritise their mitigation efforts. To this end, our approach
 314 for supporting a PIA, goes beyond a mere documentation of an organisation's data and
 315 procedures, but offers a direct connection between the data processing flows and the
 316 existing cybersecurity status of the organisation in order to identify the magnitude of
 317 privacy risks. The developed scoring system complements the systematic approach for
 318 identifying data processing flows based on *Inderdependency Graphs*, by annotating them
 319 with the risk scores of the supporting assets. APSIA is assisted by asset inventory to offer
 320 a great level of automation in the process, while the vulnerability detection capabilities
 321 contribute to the dynamicity of the tool in detecting new threats. One could argue that,
 322 APSIA is only applicable in the context of GDPR privacy impact assessment. Indeed,
 323 our method and tool have instantiated based on GDPR. Nonetheless, APSIA is based on
 324 a generic methodology and technical artifacts that can be adjusted to comply with other
 325 legal frameworks and standards and we aim to extend our tool in the future towards
 326 this direction. Overall, the GDPR requirements, along with the cybersecurity status and

Figure 2. Structural view of the APSIA methodology.

327 the privacy levels of the organisation are offered in a unified manner under the umbrella
328 of the methodology presented in the following section.

329 **3. Towards a Hybrid Risk Assessment Methodology: Unified Security & Privacy IAs**

330 In this section, we elaborate on the methodology followed to treat the cybersecurity
331 and privacy risk assessment in a unified manner and integrate the PIA as part of a dy-
332 namic iterative process of infrastructure monitoring and risk assessment. Our approach
333 capitalises on a typical risk assessment workflow, but considers the interdependence of
334 cybersecurity and privacy risks by leveraging the following technology offerings:

- 335 • The introduction of interdependency graphs, as a modelling technique and enabler,
336 for capturing and visualising the data flows and supporting assets' interdependencies
337 in the context of an organisation.
- 338 • A novel and extensible privacy risk scoring system aiming to quantify the privacy
339 risks imposed by identified vulnerabilities on ICT assets.
- 340 • A dynamic and extensible system model that maps core GDPR entities and require-
341 ments for assisting the decision makers in keeping track of all needed information
342 and assessing the degree of compliance upon the occurrence of threats.

343 In what follows, we break down the methodology's steps for regulating the hy-
344 brid assessment process of APSIA, while in the following section we elaborate on the
345 aforementioned technology offerings used to realise the methodology. Figure 2 provides
346 an overview of the methodology which consists of widely accepted steps, but aims to
347 facilitate the conduction of the cyber and privacy risk assessment in tandem:

348 **Step 1: Scope and Domain definition.** The focal point of this step is the definition
349 of the type of the assessment and the fragmentation of the specific organisation and
350 its domain (e.g. Healthcare, Energy sectors, e.t.c.). During this task, the definition of
351 the regulatory framework, the standards and guidelines that drive the operation of
352 the domain must be defined. In fact, this action point engages the principal actors of
353 the organisation to document the identified requirements. Based on the above, the
354 outcome of the analysis of the domain shall be the identification and definition of all the
355 processing activities, the corresponding assets and personnel which will be involved
356 in the assessment. Any organisation and its ICT infrastructure can be seen as a set of
357 linked assets, resources, processes which belong into the sphere of influence of diverse
358 actors who may have different access and control rights. In this direction, it is vital to
359 form a common perception of the environment, where a risk assessor aims to evaluate

360 the cybersecurity and privacy risks considering those multiple dependencies. Thus, this
361 preliminary step aims to clearly define the goals, the scope, and the envisioned outcome
362 of the assessment.

- 363 • Scope: Identification of all legacy ICT and domain-specific assets, actors, data
364 subjects, and processes that fall into the scope of the assessment methodology. All
365 the aforementioned entities are treated as tangible and intangible assets in the scope
366 of the APSIA method and tool and define the scope and the boundaries of the
367 assessment.
- 368 • Goal: Identification, analysis and assessment of the threats, vulnerabilities, funda-
369 mental rights and risks, which are associated to the assets that fall into the scope of
370 the risk assessment.
- 371 • Outcome: Evaluation of the cybersecurity and privacy risks, as a consequence of
372 the multiple asset interdependencies, that can lead to proper mitigation actions.

373 **Step 2: Assets, Processes & Dependencies analysis.** After defining the scope and
374 breaking down the domain to perform the assessment, the first step of the iterative
375 lifecycle of the assessment is the analysis of the Assets, Processes, along with their
376 interdependencies. The fundamental goal of this step is the identification and modelling
377 of the main cyber or/and physical (controlled/monitored by a cyber system) processes
378 that comprise the organisation, the detection of assets which are involved in, and their
379 dependencies. In this context, the risk assessor should perform the following activities:

- 380 • Business Processes and processing activities identification: All cyber processes of
381 interest, along with their data sources, must be defined and recorded in order to be
382 part of the evaluation process.
- 383 • Actors Association: The identified actors are linked to the defined Business Pro-
384 cesses and the corresponding assets.
- 385 • Assets Identification: All assets involved in the identified data processing activities
386 that may be part of the provision of services and their risk level needs to be evalu-
387 ated, must be identified and reported. It should be noted that the cyber assets can
388 be identified either manually or by using automated tools, e.g. network scanners.
- 389 • Assets Interdependencies Identification: Specification and Illustration of the inter-
390 connections that exist among the entities and the assets comprising the investigated
391 organisation and domain.

392 Note that, the actions of this step aim to provide an accurate reflection of the current
393 status of the operational field and the ICT infrastructure of the organisation in order to
394 provide a solid basis to the next steps of the assessment. In order to maintain this accurate
395 reflection, the aforementioned actions shall be executed every time a new assessment
396 cycle should be initiated. The initiation of this process could be triggered periodically or
397 upon the detection of an event like, among others, the detection of a new asset entry, the
398 definition of a new procession activity.

399 **Step 3: Threat & Vulnerability analysis.** This step aims to analyse and document
400 the threats and vulnerabilities that may occur against the underlined infrastructure.
401 The probability of the occurrence of a threat is a factor which may vary based on the
402 several factors, such as the nature of the infrastructure per se, the accessibility provided
403 to the targeted assets, among others. Hence, the definition of a threat probability is
404 a subjective matter which is usually undertaken by the security administrator of the
405 infrastructure. In this regard, it is vital to define the threat landscape which is a product
406 of the technologies used, potential vulnerabilities, and the historic log of cyber incidents.
407 Hence, the aim of this step is to identify the set of the applicable individual cyber threats
408 per asset. However, towards conducting the assessment in a dynamic manner, our
409 approach capitalises on vulnerability discovery tools that periodically probe the network
410 for identifying vulnerabilities on the assets of the infrastructure. Thus, this step is crucial
411 for the next steps of the utilised methodology, which aim to define the impact and risks
412 based on the dynamically monitored cybersecurity conditions of the infrastructure.

413 The cyber threat analysis can be based on the following possible sources:

- 414 • Domain knowledge of Security or Data Protection officer: These entities usually
415 have the experience to identify applicable and relevant threats to the involved
416 assets. Their insights may also base on historic records of cyber incidents that can
417 reveal weak point of the assets and specific attack patterns against them.
- 418 • Existing repositories and threat intelligence platforms: Those repositories (such as
419 NVD¹, CVE²) can offer details on existing and new threats found and documented
420 by organisations and companies active in the cyber defence field. In addition,
421 intelligent threat exchange platforms enable the participants to investigate emerging
422 threats in the wild and quickly identify if their endpoints have been compromised
423 in major cyber attacks.

424 **Step 4: Impact Analysis.** Following the traditional cyber risk assessment methodol-
425 ogy, a threat or a vulnerability exploitation can affect the three security qualities, namely
426 the Confidentiality (C), Integrity (I) and Availability (A) of a targeted asset (also known
427 as the CIA triad).

428 The impact notion in the field of the cybersecurity risk assessment is a well-known
429 and well-defined notion. However, a crucial research and practical question is how,
430 and to which extend, a vulnerability exploitation may have a cascading impact to the
431 privacy realm. In this direction, our work aims to bridge the gap between the cyber and
432 privacy risk assessment, which are treated as distinct management processes [18][19],
433 and address the cybersecurity and privacy impact assessment under a unified step in
434 the context of our methodology and technology offering. As it will be explained in detail
435 in sections 4.1 and 4.3 our method capitalises on the interdependency graph model and
436 to an expansible privacy scoring systems for quantifying the privacy impact triggered
437 by identified vulnerabilities of the ICT infrastructure in a dynamic manner.

438 **Step 5: Risk Assessment.** This step capitalizes on the outcomes of the previous
439 steps in order to proceed to the final risk estimation. After documenting the assets,
440 the actors, the business processes, the data processing activities, the vulnerabilities,
441 the threats and the associated impact, the risk assessment methodology combines this
442 information to evaluate the overall risk imposed to the infrastructure and trigger the
443 necessary reporting phase. During this phase, especially for the privacy risk assessment,
444 our approach evaluates all the interdependencies identified during the previous phases
445 of the methodology to acquire the dataflows of all the involved personal data (e.g. PII)
446 through the processing activities of the organisation, along with the imposed risk due to
447 the engagement of vulnerable supporting assets.

448 **Step 6: Risk Mitigation.** Given the results of the risk assessment processes, Mitiga-
449 tion Controls (MC) can be applied as an action for regulating the risk to the desired level.
450 In this Step, the risk level values are evaluated by the risk assessor and are compared to
451 predefined thresholds, which have been set as requirements during the initial steps on
452 the methodology. In cases where a risk exceeds the desired threshold the infrastructure
453 administrators may proceed to mitigation actions. These actions may vary based on
454 the nature of the assets, the vulnerabilities, and other requirements, such as the cost
455 and complexity of a control adoption. The adoption decision of mitigation controls is
456 undertaken by the security administrator, who has a well-established knowledge of the
457 infrastructure and the domain knowledge.

458 However, in order to support the decision making of the experts, there have been a
459 plethora of guidelines and standards that define mitigation actions. Several controls that
460 refer to procedural and technical remediation actions can be taken into consideration.
461 In the context of our methodology, since we aim to define the dependence between
462 a cyber and privacy risk, by extrapolating the former in the privacy field using the

¹ National Vulnerability Database - <https://nvd.nist.gov/>

² Common Vulnerability and Exposures - <https://cve.mitre.org/>

463 privacy scoring system, we mainly focus on mitigation actions that can mitigate the
464 cyber risk that triggers the privacy one. The arsenal of mitigation measures depends
465 on the adopted standards, guideline in the context of the organisation, but they also
466 depend on the domain and infrastructure knowledge of the engaged professional in
467 the process. Our tool utilises as a baseline the CIS controls [42], as a valuable source for
468 identifying mitigation actions that fit to the needs of several business domains. In the
469 context of the risk assessment process, once appropriate mitigation controls are applied
470 for mitigating a vulnerability or a threat on an asset (or a set of assets), the assessment
471 shall be triggered again in order to calculate the residual risk and thus, evaluate the
472 efficacy of the adopted measures.

473 Note that, the selection of optimal mitigation actions is out of the scope of the
474 proposed methodology and tool. Our aim is to support the decision makers for taking
475 informed decision during the risk mitigation lifecycle.

476 **4. APSIA Conceptual Architecture and Building Blocks**

477 The iterative steps of the APSIA methodology aim to keep the enhanced assessment
478 up-to-date and consider any changes that may (dynamically) occur in the Cyber, Physical
479 and Operational environment of the target ecosystem. APSIA is capable to support
480 and complement PIA procedures and to enhance the assessment with dynamic asset
481 inventory and vulnerability discovery techniques in order to feed the assessment steps
482 dynamically. Figure 3 presents the high-level architecture of APSIA, which highlights the
483 separation between the physical environment and the APSIA operational environment,
484 while intuitively reflects the interconnections that enable the flow of information to the
485 building blocks of APSIA.

486 **Physical Environment:** APSIA takes advantage of information regarding the tan-
487 gible and intangible assets (along with their interdependencies), the different actors,
488 threats and vulnerabilities, and the organisation's processing activities. The discovery of
489 ICT assets and vulnerabilities is achieved through the use of inventory tools (OpenVAS),
490 while the documentation of the processing activities is part of the initial configuration of
491 APSIA by the CISO or DPO of an organisation, who is aware of the data and processes
492 that should be in the scope of the assessment.

493 **APSIA Operational Environment:** The APSIA environment incorporates the nec-
494 essary building blocks for performing the assessment. More specifically, the internal
495 modeling components of APSIA generate the interdependency graph and identify the
496 chain of assets included in the processing activities. The interdependency graphs assist
497 the security analyst, to identify potential privacy risks based on a cartography of assets,
498 which encapsulate their vulnerabilities and the potential privacy threats posed against
499 them. This graph is updated every time a new assessment is conducted in order to
500 include possible updates from the assessed ecosystem. The interdependency graphs
501 are also used for constructing the data processing flows, which are formed through the
502 asset paths and data sources defined by the assessor. After defining the aforementioned
503 dependencies and having an updated reflection of the assessed environment, the Privacy
504 scoring system undertakes the quantification of the privacy threats. To do so, the scoring
505 system is based on risk factors of existing repositories, such as CVE, but can be extended
506 by other context dimensions.

507 The following sections elaborate on each of the APSIA building blocks by providing
508 more details on their structure and functional behavior.

509 *4.1. Interdependency Graphs for Data and Asset Modelling*

510 In order to meet the requirement of a cyber and privacy risk assessment method-
511 ology, our work capitalises on a graphical representation, namely the interdependency
512 graphs [43,44]. This particular representation offers the necessary flexibility to define
513 relations among large number of objects of arbitrary types, and thus, provides a model
514 that can be adapted to the needs of the risk assessor of virtually any kind of organisation.

Figure 3. APSIA Conceptual Architecture

515 This graphical representation model is a cornerstone in our work, as it works as the
 516 “glue” that holds together ICT assets, data entries, threats and vulnerabilities in order to
 517 identify risky data processing activities of an organization.

518 Our densely interconnected world is based on the provision of services that may
 519 form rather complex flows of data processing activities, which engage actors and sup-
 520 porting assets which may be distributed, not only on a network basis, but also across
 521 different physical locations. Thus, keeping track of these workflows implies the need of a
 522 modelling techniques that can meet the challenges introduced in modern infrastructures
 523 that store, process and require the exchange of data. This mesh of interrelations results in
 524 a very sensitive network of critical entities, where the various types of interdependencies
 525 have to be identified in the context an assessment.

526 The interdependency graph model allows physical, cyber, and human elements
 527 to be combined, including combinations of legacy systems and new technologies, and
 528 data. More precisely, in order to be able to have a global view of the infrastructure and
 529 the workflows of data processing and be in position to detect possible cascading and
 530 escalating effects of threats against users’ privacy, it is crucial to maintain a cartography
 531 of all the dependent assets. In the model, Nodes are used to represent the individual
 532 assets and edges to represent the interdependencies amongst them. In [45] four general
 533 types of interdependencies have been identified: physical, cyber, geographical, and
 534 logical. Depending on the granularity of the performed analysis, some of these types
 535 can be omitted. In our work we use the interdependency types *IsConnectedTo*, *IsUsedBy*,
 536 *IsProcessedBy*, *isLocatedIn*, *isStoredOn* and *IsInstalledOn* to annotate the relation among
 537 assets. These relations are not only used to denote connections among tangible ICT
 538 assets, but also intangible ones, such as data, health records and PIIs. The *IsConnectedTo*
 539 and *IsInstalledOn* represents network and systemic inter-dependencies, the *IsUsedBy* and
 540 *isLocatedIn* represent physical inter-dependencies, the *IsProcessedBy* and *isStoredOn* rep-
 541 resent logical inter-dependencies. Each type/dependency is represented by a different
 542 edge arrow.

543 Overall, by utilizing the interdependency graphs, the risk assessor is in position
 544 to identify on-the-fly potential privacy risks based on a cartography of assets, which
 545 encapsulate their vulnerabilities and the potential privacy threats posed against them.
 546 In this way, the graph model contributes, not only to the uncovering of privacy risky
 547 individual assets, but crucially, it ease in highlighting privacy risky paths which are
 548 formed by chains of assets included in a specific processing activity. An example of an
 549 interdependency is illustrated in Figure 5.

550 Hence, our modelling techniques is a cornerstone that supports the methodology
551 adopted in this work, while the key functionalities that this component is offering are:

- 552 • The asset representation, along with the interdependencies that connect both tangi-
553 ble (e.g. a Database) and intangible assets (e.g. health records).
- 554 • Constitutes the steppingstone for defining the Processing Activities, since each
555 Processing Activity is represented as a chain of supporting assets.
- 556 • Gives the ability to detect, in how many processing activities a vulnerable asset is
557 engaged in order to assist the privacy scoring system (see Section 4.3) to quantify
558 the imposed privacy impact score.
- 559 • Last but not least, works as the connection point between the privacy impact scoring
560 system and the Data processing flows (see Section 4.2), as the GDPR data processing
561 activities inherit the privacy risk levels of their supporting ICT assets.

562 4.2. Data Processing Flows in the Frame of GDPR

563 The Processing Activity is a principal aspect of the GDPR and aggregates all the
564 GDPR-related information. To form the processing activities, we utilise a dynamic
565 and extensible model which is able to maintain a map among the core GDPR entities
566 and requirements, and the processed data. As mentioned in the previous section, the
567 formation of the Processing Activities is based on the asset modelling, which maintains
568 a representation of the tangible and intangible asset chains. The exact GDPR entities
569 and the formation of the processing activities is part of the initial configuration, which is
570 undertaken by the security analysts or the risk assessor (e.g. CISO and/or DPO) of the
571 organisation.

572 Hence, the Processing Activity is the key aspect of the GDPR modelling that enables
573 the assessor to understand how data flow among the organisation's processes and which
574 entities are engaged in it. The main information that a Processing Activity includes can
575 be divided in three parts: a) the processing purpose along with the involved entities, b)
576 all the processed data assigned to specific Subjects, and c) the asset chain that is involved
577 in the processing activity. The *IsProcessedBy* interdependency introduced in the previous
578 section enables the functionality of forming the Processing Activities as a chain of assets.
579 Processing Activities are an important part for the overall functionality, as the privacy
580 risk calculation formula considers the *scope of impact* factor (see Section 4.3.2) to calculate
581 the privacy score.

582 Indicatively, in a Processing Activity, among other attributes, we define the data
583 subject, data controller, the data processor, the legal grounds, the data recipients, the
584 processing country, processing purpose and lawfulness of processing, all the involved
585 personal data (e.g. PII such as the name, surname, etc.), and all the assets that are
586 included in this processing activity. Those attributes are combined together through the
587 use of interdependency graphs.

588 4.3. Privacy Impact Scoring System

589 As mentioned in the introduction of this work, the current privacy risk assessment
590 methods and tools perform the risk assessment by ignoring the cybersecurity state of the
591 underlined infrastructure. In fact, the reported tools in section 2 base the assessment on
592 documenting the organisation's procedures and the definition of the final risk depends
593 completely on the perception of the administrator. In fact, one of the current scoring sys-
594 tems shortfalls is the lack of a risk scoring system that adequately considers the context
595 of the environment for identified vulnerabilities[46]. This can lead the organisations to
596 improperly prioritise their mitigation efforts. In the frame of our method and tool, the
597 context is the data subject's privacy and our aim is to provide a formula which considers
598 the peculiarities of the organisation's data processing procedures along with its cyber
599 security state.

600 Current methods for analysing identified cyber vulnerabilities of traditional infor-
601 mation technology systems tend to focus on the impact to systems' CIA triad to discern

602 end-user risks. Although this approach is sufficient for evaluating traditional informa-
603 tion technology systems, it fails to consider the operational ramifications for complex
604 systems-of-systems. Thus, there is a need for a Risk Scoring System that provides the
605 means to characterize identified vulnerabilities and numerically score the effect that a
606 potential exploitation of a vulnerability may have on users' privacy.

607 To address this limitation, approach quantifies the privacy risk based on a generic
608 and extensible scoring system, which takes into consideration, not only the vulnerability
609 score per se, but also the potential impact to patient's privacy. This scoring system will be
610 used to measure the privacy impact of the data processing activities of an organisation,
611 given the vulnerabilities of the supporting assets. Given that GDPR compliance is
612 necessary for organisations, this scoring system can contribute towards measuring the
613 degree of GDPR compliance.

614 The developed scoring system incorporates two primary factors, which are used to
615 calculate a Total Score: (i) Vulnerability Characterization, and (emphii Privacy Impact.
616 On the one hand, the vulnerability characterization refers to the details and the severity
617 of the vulnerability, which in turn may threaten a user's privacy. On the other, the
618 Privacy impact is based on three contributing factors, namely:

- 619 a the level of impact on the fundamental rights and freedoms of the individuals
- 620 b the scope of impact to the data processing activities
- 621 c the type (i.e., sensitivity) of the processed data

622 By combining these two elements, the scoring system provides the mean for reflecting
623 the severity of an identified vulnerability in the context of users' privacy.

624 In the context of our work, the vulnerability score is based on the Common Vulner-
625 ability Scoring System (CVSS)³, where a value from 0 to 10 is assigned to the identified
626 vulnerability, following the system's scoring formulas. However, the determination of
627 the privacy impact is based on the aforementioned contributing factors, which will be
628 explained in detail in Section 4.3.2.

629 The final score and the contributing factors follow the structure depicted in Figure 4.
630 While the scoring algorithm combines these two factors, it treats the impact as the leading
631 factor for the final assessment. Indeed, it uses a weighted scale to focus on the impact to
632 users' privacy, while incorporating the vulnerability score. The scores are evaluated on
633 a 0 to 10 scale, with higher numbers indicating more severe ratings. It must be stated
634 that the exact value of the weights is a parameter that can be adjusted accordingly, given
635 the preferences and the domain knowledge of experts of the organisation. The weighted
636 scale formula is given in Equation 1.

$$\text{Privacy Score} = (\text{Vulnerability Characterization} + 2 \times \text{Privacy Impact}) / 3 \quad (1)$$

637 4.3.1. Vulnerability characterisation

638 A vulnerability may appear either as a technical limitation of a system, or a gap
639 in the security procedures and practices of an organisation. We base our method on
640 dynamically detecting vulnerabilities by deploying the OpenVAS Vulnerability Assess-
641 ment Scanner⁴. In this way, we create a dependence between the infrastructure's asset
642 and their vulnerabilities. The most prominent way of quantifying the severity and the
643 impact that a vulnerability may have on a targeting system, is the adoption of a common
644 and vendor-independent scoring system enables the security society, and especially the
645 risk assessors, to form a common understanding for the criticality level of vulnerabilities.
646 In the context of distributed organisations, there is a need for privacy assessment tool to
647 be deployed on different sites, and thus, the use of an open, independent and globally
648 accepted scoring system is of significant importance in forming a common risk percep-

³ Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) - <https://www.first.org/cvss/>

⁴ OpenVAS: Open Vulnerability Assessment Scanner- <https://www.openvas.org/>

Figure 4. Structural view of Privacy score with the contributing factors.

649 tion among the involved parties. The utilisation of CVSS contributes to the design of
 650 a unified risk assessment methodology that leaves aside the diversity of the engaged
 651 assets. In fact, depending on the domain, an organisation may utilise a wide range of
 652 legacy ICT and domain-specific devices (e.g., IoT, Industrial, Energy, healthcare devices)
 653 and applications. Inevitably, such a setup results to an extended attack surface (more
 654 vulnerabilities) against a significant amount of data processing activities of Personally
 655 Identifiable Information (PII), and thus, an increased possibility of data leakage.

656 Last but not least, the adoption of CVSS enables the risk calculations can be com-
 657 patible both for vulnerabilities of old and legacy ICT assets, as for new ones, and are
 658 in-line with global vulnerability repositories. It has to be stated that this is a requirement
 659 that must be satisfied by the developed privacy assessment methodology. Crucially, the
 660 adoption of CVSS guarantees that all the developed components and automated tools
 661 used for threat and vulnerability detection have a common reference point that enhances
 662 their interoperability towards the dynamic conduction of the privacy impact assessment.

663 Given the above, the vulnerability characterization aims to measure the severity
 664 of the vulnerability under the traditional risk assessment perspective. Note that the
 665 vulnerability characterization is one of the contributing factors of the Score Formula 1
 666 and is responsible for reflecting the cyber security status of the assets in the organisation.

$$Vulnerability\ Characterisation = (0.6 \times Impact + 0.4 \times Exploitability - 1.5) \times f(impact) \quad (2)$$

$$Impact = 10.41 \times (1 - (1 - ConfImpact) \times (1 - IntegImpact) \times (1 - AvailImpcat))$$

$$Exploitability = 20 \times AccessComplexity \times Authentication \times AccessVector$$

$$f(impact) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{impact} = 0 \\ 1.176 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

667 4.3.2. Privacy Impact

668 The Privacy impact reflects the consequences an exploited vulnerability may have
 669 on a data subject's privacy. As have been already stated, one of the current scoring
 670 systems shortfalls is the lack of a risk scoring system that adequately considers the
 671 context of the environment for identified vulnerabilities. Thus, the utilisation of a
 672 scoring system that focuses exclusively on the impact on CIA metrics, fails to consider
 673 the operational ramifications imposed to the affected organisation. To address this
 674 issue, the proposed scoring system incorporates the privacy impact as contributing
 675 factor, to extrapolate the vulnerability exploitation impact to the privacy dimension.
 676 The privacy impact itself consists three components, namely, a) the level of impact on
 677 the fundamental rights and freedoms of the individuals, b) the scope of impact to the
 678 data processing activities, and c) the type (i.e., sensitivity) of the processed data. The
 679 aforementioned components and their contribution in the scoring formula are described
 680 in the following sections.

$$Privacy\ Impact = Level\ of\ Impact + Scope\ of\ Impact + Data\ type \quad (3)$$

681 A. Level of Impact

682 The level of impact aims to assess the impact on the fundamental rights and free-
 683 doms of the individuals, resulting from the possible loss of security of the personal data.
 684 Four levels of impact are considered (Low, Medium, High, Very High) as shown in Table
 685 1, following the taxonomy proposed by ENISA for the personal data processing [47]
 686 considering also the case where there is no impact to the rights and freedoms of the
 687 individual. As can be inferred by the taxonomy proposed by ENISA, the lowest level
 688 of impact considers minor consequences on individuals, while at the highest level, the
 689 affected individuals may suffer significant or even irreversible consequences. Although
 690 this taxonomy has been adopted on ENISA's tool [33] for evaluating the level of risk of
 691 personal data processing operations, the determination of the appropriate value relies
 692 explicitly on the situational awareness and the domain experience of the assessor. In
 693 the context of the scoring formula of this work, the exact level of impact is determined
 694 based on a systematic approach which considers the type of the vulnerability which
 695 targets an asset, as well as the importance of the latter in data processing activities of the
 696 organisation. In this way, the scoring system considers the nature of the vulnerability
 697 which targets an asset and the privacy-oriented business value of it.

Table 1. Impact categories on the fundamental rights and freedoms of the individuals, resulting from the possible loss of security of the personal data according to ENISA

Level of Impact	Description	Value
None	Individual will not encounter inconveniences or consequences	0.0
Low	Individuals may encounter a few minor inconveniences, which they will overcome without any problem (time spent re-entering information, annoyances, irritations, etc.).	1.0
Medium	Individuals may encounter significant inconveniences, which they will be able to overcome despite a few difficulties (extra costs, denial of access to business services, fear, lack of understanding, stress, minor physical ailments, etc.).	2.5
High	Individuals may encounter significant consequences, which they should be able to overcome albeit with serious difficulties (misappropriation of funds, blacklisting by financial institutions, property damage, loss of employment, subpoena, worsening of health, etc.).	4.5
Very High	Individuals which may encounter significant, or even irreversible consequences, which they may not overcome (inability to work, long-term psychological or physical ailments, death, etc.).	7.0

698 **Vulnerability type:** In order to identify the type of the vulnerability, we adopted
 699 the taxonomy used by CVEdetails online vulnerability database⁵ . CVEdetails provides
 700 an easy to access interface to CVE vulnerability data. Vulnerabilities are categorised
 701 based on vendors, products, and versions. CVE vulnerability data are taken from
 702 National Vulnerability Database (NVD) xml feeds provided by NIST. Additional data
 703 from several sources like exploits from exploit-db⁶, vendor statements and additional
 704 vendor supplied data, Metasploit modules are also published in addition to NVD CVE
 705 data. Hence, CVEdetails is a database which enriches the basic CVEs with additional
 706 metadata and offers a classification that reveals 13 type of the vulnerabilities, as can be
 707 seen below.

- | | | | |
|-----|---------------------|-----|---------------------------|
| 708 | • Denial of Service | 715 | • XSS |
| 709 | • Bypass Something | 716 | • Directory Traversal |
| 710 | • Execute Code | 717 | • File Inclusion |
| 711 | • Gain Information | 718 | • Memory Corruption |
| 712 | • Overflow | 719 | • CSRF |
| 713 | • Gain Privilege | 720 | • Http Response Splitting |
| 714 | • SQL Injection | | |

721 The type of a vulnerability is a parameter of significant importance that enhances
 722 the situational awareness of a security defender when it comes to the prioritisation of
 723 actions for mitigating cyber risks. The same applies in the case where the defender
 724 must make decisions considering the data protection and the user privacy. For instance,
 725 vulnerabilities of the Gain Information or the SQL Injection categories, can have a
 726 greater impact on users' privacy in contrast to a Denial of Service, which mainly affect
 727 the availability of a source. Given the above, the proposed scoring system takes into
 728 consideration the type of the vulnerability in order to convey this information to the final
 729 score, which will be used by the decision maker in the privacy risk mitigation actions.

730 **Sensitivity of ICT asset:** In order to define the level of impact in a more reliable
 731 way, the privacy sensitivity of an asset is considered. More specifically, as the infrastruc-
 732 ture assets are engaged in the data processing activities of an organisation, undoubtedly
 733 some may have a more crucial role in the data processing contrary to others that simply
 734 support the activity. For example, a central database which is used to store the Personal
 735 or Sensitive information of a hospital's patients, is of greater importance -in terms of
 736 privacy- than an ICT network component. To materialise this, we use a 4-tier scale to
 737 categorise the assets into the Low, Medium, High, Very High tiers. Given the above,
 738 the scoring system takes into consideration the importance of the assets in order to
 739 convey this information to the final score, which will be used by the decision maker in
 740 the privacy risk mitigation actions. The definition of the level of impact factor is the
 741 product of the two above-mentioned notions namely, the *type of the vulnerability* and the
 742 *sensitivity of the assets*, following the mapping illustrated in Table 2. It must be stated
 743 that the mapping has been generated based on the domain knowledge of cybersecurity
 744 experts and penetration testers of our corporate environment, who have the necessary
 745 experience to perceive how a specific type of a vulnerability can affect privacy-sensitive
 746 assets. Although the proposed mapping conveys the domain knowledge of experts, it
 747 cannot be considered foolproof, as security experts of different expertise and different
 748 organisations may have a different point of view on the mapping. The exact definition of
 749 the map is part of the configuration steps of the tool and depend also on the cybersecurity
 750 posture and risk appetite of the assessor.

⁵ The ultimate vulnerability datasource - <https://www.cvedetails.com/>

⁶ Exploit Database - Exploits for Penetration Testers - <https://www.exploit-db.com/>

Asset sensitivity	Vulnerability Type													
	DoS	Code Execution	Overflow	Memory Corruption	SQL Injection	XSS	Directory Traversal	Http Response	Bypass something	Gain Information	Gain Privileges	CSRF	File inclusion	
Low	L	M	L	L	M	L	L	L	L	M	L	L	L	
Medium	L	M	M	M	M	M	L	L	M	M	M	M	M	
High	L	VH	H	M	VH	H	M	M	H	VH	VH	H	H	
Very High	L	VH	H	H	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	VH	

Table 2: Definition of the level of impact factor as a product of the *type of a vulnerability* and the *sensitivity of an asset*

751 B. Scope of impact

752 The scope of impact is used to reflect the number of data processing activities
753 affected by an instance of exploiting the vulnerability. The data processing activities may
754 consist of several supporting assets which are used to process, store, and visualise the
755 data. However, those assets may have vulnerabilities which can impose a risk to the
756 processing activities in which they are engaged. In this direction, the scoring algorithm
757 considers the scope of impact factor in order to reflect the severity that the vulnerability
758 exploitation may have to the dependent processing activities. Hence, three options
759 have been identified based on the impact values, namely *Single* ($value \leq 0.5$), *Multi*
760 ($0.5 < value \leq 1.0$), and *All* ($1.0 < value \leq 1.5$). Following this approach, the scoring
761 system takes into consideration the dependence between the vulnerable assets and the
762 data processing activities of the organisation and conveys this information to the final
763 score, which will be used by the decision maker in the privacy risk mitigation actions.

764 C. Data types

765 Information systems may store and process a huge amount of data. However, the
766 criticality of the data is not always the same. For instance, some processing activities
767 may focus on publicly available data, others on financial data, and other personal or
768 even sensitive data. This variation indicates the need to assign a different criticality
769 levels to the aforementioned data types and treat personal and sensitive data, as data
770 types that can clearly have a higher impact on the fundamental rights and freedoms of
771 the individuals in case of data breaches [48]. To materialize this in the proposed method,
772 the data that an organisation stores/processes, are classified in the following categories,
773 following the classification proposed in [49].

- 774 • *Sensitive personal data* (medical data, legal documents, etc.)
- 775 • *Personal data* (data which uniquely identify a person, such as IDs, Social Security
776 Number (SSN), personal or marital status, etc.)
- 777 • *Financial data* (data related to financial transactions, accounting entries, etc.)
- 778 • *Operational data* (data generated during the execution of a service, log files, etc.)
- 779 • *Other data* (data that cannot be classified in any of the above categories, and belong
780 to a lower criticality level)

781 Thus, each data entry, which is part of a processing activity, falls into one these
782 categories and the privacy scoring algorithm considers the criticality of the processed
783 data. Given the above, this property is reflected to the final score, which will be used by
784 the decision maker in the privacy risk mitigation actions.

Table 3: Data Type values.

Data Type	Value
Sensitive Personal Data	1.5
Personal Data	1.0
Financial Data	0.75
Operational Data	0.5
Other Data	0

785 4.3.3. Privacy scores of processing activities

786 Given the methodology steps described in section 3 and the privacy impact scoring
 787 of section 4.3, one can infer that based on the interdependencies of the tangible and
 788 intangible assets of an organisation, a vulnerable asset may trigger a privacy threat.
 789 Thus, the privacy scoring formula given in 1 is calculated per vulnerability and per
 790 asset. Hence, the scoring approach produces as many privacy scores as the existing
 791 vulnerabilities on the assets. This is reasonable, as each vulnerability may trigger a
 792 different privacy impact.

793 Having said that, overall we define 3 different types of scores:

- 794 • the asset-level privacy score (APS)
- 795 • the processing activity-level privacy score (PAPS)
- 796 • the organisation-level (global) privacy score (OPS)

797 All three scores range between 0 and 10. The corresponding qualitative value is
 798 mapped to a 5-tier scale values ranging from “Very Low” to “Very High”, as can be seen
 799 in 4.

Table 4: 5-tier scale values for privacy score.

Privacy score range	Qualitative Value
0.0 - 2.0	Very Low
2.0 - 4.0	Low
4.0 - 6.0	Medium
6.0 - 8.0	High
8.0 - 10	Very High

800 *Asset-level privacy score (APS):* An asset-level privacy score is assigned to
 801 each asset, associated with a vulnerability, following the scoring system presented in
 802 Section 4.3. It must be noted that in the case where an asset is affected by multiple
 803 vulnerabilities, the highest value (*max*) among the Asset-level privacy scores will be
 804 assigned to the asset. The privacy score is calculated following formula 1.

805 *Processing activity-level privacy score (PAPS):* Each processing activity is represented
 806 as a chain of interrelated assets (supporting assets). Thus, the highest Asset-level privacy
 807 score among the assets of the processing activity represents the privacy risk of the activity.
 808 For instance, the privacy score assigned to the Processing Activity *i* that contains *n* assets
 809 in its asset chain is calculated based on the following formula:

$$PAPS_i = \max(APS_1, APS_2, \dots, APS_n) \quad (4)$$

810 *Organisation-level (Global) privacy score (OPS):* The global privacy score is the highest
 811 Asset-level privacy score among all the ICT assets of the infrastructure of the organisation.
 812 Thus, the highest Asset-level privacy score among the assets of the organisation, and
 813 in turn among all the processing activities, represents the global privacy score of an
 814 organisation. For instance, the privacy score assigned to the organisation that contains *k*
 815 assets in its infrastructure is formalised as follows:

$$OPS = \max(APS_1, APS_2, \dots APS_k) \quad (5)$$

816 The selection of the highest score to be represented in the APS, PAPS and OPS
817 scores aims to simplify the assessment process, especially in the cases where a great
818 number of assets and processing activities is engaged in an organisation. In addition, this
819 quick view can be beneficial in cases where the lifecycle of the methodology described
820 in section 3, is triggered periodically or upon the detection of events that can trigger the
821 assessment process in a dynamic manner (e.g. detection of new vulnerability, new asset
822 entry in a processing activity, new device in the topology).

823 However, in order not to miss the holistic view of the threats and their correspond-
824 ing risks, in case where multiple risks exist for an assets, a histogram is generated to
825 complement the analysis and represent the distributional characteristics of the risks for
826 the assets. In this way, the histogram balances the narrow view of focusing solely to
827 most severe privacy impact. Section 5 elaborates on the aforementioned points in the
828 frame of a case study of a healthcare organisation.

829 5. Case Study for the Healthcare Sector

830 This section demonstrates the applicability of the APSIA methodology and tool
831 in a case study of a hospital. The case study considers security and privacy concerns
832 against the hospital's ICT infrastructure that threaten processing activities. The case
833 study is based on actual requirements driven from a real use case in the context of the
834 H2020 CUREX project [50]. More specifically, during the testing process of APSIA we
835 approached a set of healthcare related stakeholders, ranging from the IT support team
836 and the security administrator of a hospital to physicians, for acquiring information
837 regarding the actual assets, medical devices and processes which shall be considered in a
838 healthcare environment. Based on this information, we fleshed out the actual topology of
839 ICT assets and applications along with their interdependencies, and we defined the data
840 and the processing activities. The gathered information was used to create an accurate
841 virtual topology in order to simulate in a lab environment the existence of vulnerable
842 devices that support the hospital's data processing activities and may trigger privacy
843 risks. APSIA deployed in a virtual machine to ensure network visibility and enable asset
844 inventory and vulnerability detection. The generated setup of all the aforementioned
845 aspects of the virtual environment and the visualisation results shown in Appendix
846 A, were then ratified by the board of relevant professionals of the CUREX project, who
847 identified the value of APSIA.

848 More specifically, the IT infrastructure of the hospital facilitates the deployment
849 of Healthcare Point of Care (POC) technologies. POC have been widely used during
850 the last decade to pave the way to the emergence of healthcare monitoring and man-
851 agement. POC technologies are hospital information systems that includes terminals
852 or other devices for medical diagnostic testing at or near the site of patient care [51].
853 The advances of POC have enabled patients to receive better care. However, along with
854 these advances, there are concerns regarding the connectivity of these devices to the
855 Internet or to a Health Information System (HIS), since it may affect both the security
856 and the privacy of a patient. Even though, the connected medical devices improve the
857 quality of patients' care, they also expose a wide attack surface and introduce new and
858 domain-specific vulnerabilities. In addition, the rising number of the processed personal
859 data in conjunction with the increasing data breaches has led to an attention towards
860 data protection and privacy. Hospitals and care centers need to address these challenges
861 by efficiently assessing the privacy risks in tandem with GDPR that mandates such an
862 assessment. To this end, in our scenario we consider a subset of common assets and
863 devices that exist in a hospital's POC to demonstrate the APSIA methodology and tool.

Figure 5. Asset interdependency graph with the processing activities highlighted

864 5.1. Scenario Overview

865 Patients *Patient1*, *Patient2* with diabetes want to perform a regular check-up. *Patient1*
 866 is visiting the *Hospital* for the first time and, hence, a registration process is initiated
 867 for collecting personal information. After the registration phase, a *Doctor* monitors
 868 their blood pressure and glucose considering their clinical history of diabetes. Two
 869 common processing activities are identified in the aforementioned scenario a) *Patient*
 870 *Registration* and b) *Patient Monitoring*. In the former processing activity, we assume
 871 patient's registration to the hospital, where the hospital's secretary *Secretary1* inserts into
 872 the HIS details such as their full name, their contact details etc.. In the latter processing
 873 activity, we assume the monitoring and storing of the patient's blood pressure and
 874 glucose measurements to the hospital's HIS.

875 Each processing activity includes a chain of assets considering the interdependen-
 876 cies among them. The hospital's CISO or DPO, periodically performs internal interviews,
 877 as a part of her role, in order to confirm the GDPR compliance levels of the organisation.
 878 In this sense, she is already aware of the processing activities that should be documented
 879 in order to keep track of how sensitive or personal data flow among the various entities
 880 and supporting assets. Overall, by utilising the interdependency graphs, a security
 881 analyst of the hospital, will be in position to identify potential privacy risks based on a
 882 cartography of assets, which encapsulate their vulnerabilities and the potential privacy
 883 threats posed against them.

884 5.2. Assessment Results

885 **Interdependency Graph:** Ten tangible assets and three intangible (e.g. data and
 886 personnel) are included with different connections among them. Figure 5 illustrates
 887 the interdependency graph of the scenario. In the *Patient Registration* processing activ-
 888 ity the engaged assets are the *Client Application*, *PC002*, *Secretary*, *HospitalServer1*, *the*
 889 *SQLServer* and *the Personal Data* (red color), while in the *Patient Monitoring* the included
 890 assets are the *Glucose Meter*, *Blood Pressure Monitor*, *Doctor*, *PC001*, *Client Application*,
 891 *HospitalServer1*, *SQLServer* and *Health Records* (green color). As can be seen, the Health
 892 Records and Personal Data nodes *isStoredOn* on the *SQLServer*. The latter *IsInstalledOn*
 893 the *HospitalServer1*, while a *ClientApplication* *IsConnectedTo* to the same server. The
 894 *Doctor* interacts with the *PC0001* based on the physical interaction *IsUsedBy*.

895 It becomes obvious that several interconnections can be defined as a result of the
 896 actual dependencies of cyber assets, data sources and actors. Especially for large scale or
 897 dynamic environments, our approach can be proved beneficial as it offers a cartography

Table 5: Use case threats, assets and privacy scores association.

ID	Asset	Vulnerability	Vulnerab. Charact. ¹	Asset Sensit.	Vuln. Type	Level of Impact	Scope of Impact	Data Type	Privacy Impact ²	Privacy Score ³
ID-01	SQLServer	CVE-2020-11898	6.4	VH	Gain Info	VH (7.0)	All (1.5)	Sensitive (1.5)	VH (10)	VH (8.8)
ID-02	Glucose Meter	CVE-2019-10964	5.8	H	Bypass Auth.	H (4.5)	Single (0.5)	Sensitive (1.5)	H (6.5)	H (6.3)
ID-03	Blood P. Mon	CVE-2017-11579	4.8	H	Gain Info	VH (7.0)	Single (0.5)	Sensitive (1.5)	VH (9)	H(7.6)
ID-04	PC0001	CVE-2017-13993	9.3	H	Code Exec.	VH (7.0)	Single (0.5)	Sensitive (1.5)	VH (9)	VH (9.1)
ID-05	PC0001	CVE-2019-1343	7.1	H	DoS	L (1.0)	Single (0.5)	Sensitive (1.5)	L (3)	M (4.4)
ID-06	PC0002	CVE-2019-5831	6.8	H	DoS	L (1.0)	Single (0.5)	Personal (1)	L (2.5)	L (3.9)

¹ Following CVSS v2 and formula 2.

² Following formula 3.

³ Following formula 1.

898 that can assist the assessor to understand how the interconnected assets facilitate the data
 899 flows of the procession activities. In this way, the interdependency graphs contribute,
 900 not only to the uncovering of privacy risks on individual assets, but crucially, they ease
 901 in highlighting privacy risky paths which are formed by chains of assets.

902 **Privacy scoring system:** As aforementioned, our proposed asset-centric scoring
 903 system incorporates the privacy impact as contributing factor for quantifying the impact
 904 that a vulnerability may have on user's privacy. Table 5, provides an overview of
 905 the vulnerabilities of core assets which are engaged in the processing activities of the
 906 organisation. As can be seen, independently of the vulnerability characterisation score,
 907 which reflects the cybersecurity criticality against the CIA triad, based on the introduced
 908 privacy scoring system the risk assessor can have the impact reflection of this cyber
 909 threat to the privacy dimension.

910 Considering the peculiarities of each case, i.e., the sensitivity of the affected asset, the
 911 vulnerability type, the type of processed data and the number of the affected processing
 912 activities (scope of impact), our scoring system calculates the Privacy Impact score and
 913 the Privacy score. In this way, in the context of a privacy impact assessment, where
 914 mitigation actions should be driven by setting the privacy preservation as the main goal
 915 to achieve, the assessor can take advantage of the privacy impact and score to clearly
 916 identify the potential privacy risks and prioritise the mitigation actions accordingly.

917 By taking a closer look at the scores of Table 5, one can notice that for ID-01, the
 918 SQLServer can be affected by a vulnerability that can lead to leak of information. Such
 919 a type of threat against a sensitive asset (in terms of privacy) can have a major impact
 920 to data subjects' privacy. However, if the assessor prioritise the mitigation actions
 921 following solely the CVSS score (Vulnerability characterisation), the ID-05 case, would
 922 look more severe, even though the ID-01 case has a direct impact of users privacy via
 923 the information leakage. In fact, the same applies for the case of ID-06. In consideration
 924 of the potential impact that CVE-2020-11898 may have on patients' privacy, our risk
 925 scoring system considers the severity of the vulnerability, but via the weighted scale
 926 of formula 1 the final score focuses on the privacy aspect. Hence, the scoring system
 927 addresses the need of considering the operational ramifications posed by the domain
 928 and quantifies the privacy risk based on an extensible scoring system. The same applies
 929 in the cases of ID-02 and ID-03, where the medical devices have been found vulnerable
 930 to Authentication Bypass and Gain Information attacks. Again in both cases, the final
 931 privacy score results to a higher score than the vulnerability characterisation and assists
 932 the assessor to notice the privacy risk from the pertinent point of view. In the case of
 933 ID-04, the code execution vulnerability of PC0001, leads to an almost equal privacy score
 934 as the vulnerability characterisation.

935 **Data processing flows in the frame of GDPR:** As we analysed thoroughly in section
 936 4.2, one of the main contributions of APSIA is the formation of the data processing flows
 937 in the context of an organisation following the principles of GDPR. Thus, given the use
 938 case scenario and the *Patient Registration* and *Patient Monitoring* processing activities,

939 Figures A1 to A3 are generated automatically by considering the interconnections of the
940 interdependency graph of Figure 5.

941 More specifically, Figure A1 creates a flow that maps the *PII, Data subjects, (i.e.*
942 *Patient1, Patient2), Purpose of processing and the Lawfulness of Processing* for revealing what
943 type of data are processed in the organisation's processing activities and under which
944 conditions and legal grounds. Note that, this view can be modified in order to provide a
945 mapping among various GDPR entities and requirements in order to give the necessary
946 flexibility to the assessor to keep track of particular flows of interest.

947 Moreover, Figures A2 and A3 present the data flows visualisation of the two identified
948 processing activities. Each data flow consists of the *PII, Data Subjects, Processing*
949 *Activities, the supporting assets and the corresponding Privacy Risks*. This type of figures
950 enables the assessor to associate the identified privacy threats, based on the privacy
951 scoring system, with the assets that trigger the threat, the data and the individuals which
952 are being threaten. This graph enables the assessor not only to prioritise the mitigation
953 actions for specific assets, but crucially, to keep track of the data of subjects that may face
954 an impact on their fundamental rights and freedoms.

955 Taking a closer look at Figure A2, the *Patient Registration* activity and the corre-
956 sponding data subjects can be affected by vulnerabilities identified in assets PC0002
957 and SQLServer. The total risk score assigned to the specific process is "Very High" and
958 overshadows the "Low" risk of PC0002, following the approach described in Section
959 4.3.3. The same approach is illustrated in Figure A3 for the *Patient Monitoring* activity. In
960 this case, more supporting assets bring threats against the data processing activity. In the
961 case of the PC0001, which was found vulnerable to DoS and Code Execution attacks, the
962 latter privacy risk overshadows the "Medium" risk of the DoS vulnerability, following
963 the approach described in Section 4.3.3.

964 Apart from the data flow graphs, APSIA offers a set of adjustable visualisation
965 tools that enhance the risk assessment process. Indicatively, Figure A4 presents the
966 heat-maps and histograms with information regarding both the privacy and the cyber
967 risks in order to provide an holistic view of the privacy and cybersecurity levels of
968 the organisation. More specifically the *Threat Probability - Vulnerability Impact* heat-map
969 provides an overview of the cybersecurity risk assessment based on the CVSS scores
970 given in Table 5. The privacy impact assessment process is supported by the heat-map
971 in Figure A4, where the correlation of the *Privacy Impact - Vulnerability Characterisation*
972 is given. As can be seen, based on the scores of Table 5, there are risk associations
973 that reveal a "Very High" privacy impact even if the vulnerability characterisation is
974 "Medium". By utilising this view, the risk assessor can properly prioritise the mitigation
975 actions based on the heat of the privacy impact axis.

976 In addition, in an effort to provide an holistic view of the Privacy scoring results of
977 the organisation, the histogram in Figure A4 presents the distributional characteristics
978 of the privacy scores for all the processing activities of the organisation. This view
979 complements the data flows in which some of the identified privacy scores may be
980 overshadowed, as only the highest score is illustrated following the approach described
981 in Section 4.3.3. Last but not least, APSIA is able to represent the evolution of risks
982 among consecutive risk assessments by highlighting the differences in the histograms.
983 Such differences may occur as a result of mitigation actions or the emergence of new
984 cybersecurity and privacy threats.

985 Overall, APSIA offers a gamut of enablers to converge and automate the privacy and
986 cybersecurity risk assessment by integrating asset inventory and vulnerability detection
987 tools to support the assessment on a dynamic manner. The visualisation options based
988 on the use of the interdependency graphs and the data processing flows constitute one
989 of the competitive advantages of APSIA. In fact, as highlighted by the authors in [23],
990 the CNIL method, which is one of the most prominent methods in the PIA field, does
991 not use visual representations of the information flows. Such a feature is the foundation
992 stone for the whole PIA and is facilitated by APSIA to a great extend.

993 6. Cybersecurity and Privacy Risk Assessment: The Road Ahead

994 While the area of risk assessment is rather mature, as aforementioned, the landscape
995 of privacy impact assessment is fragmented into various families based on emerging
996 research challenges. Undoubtedly, converging the usually contradicting security and
997 privacy requirements towards a better risk assessment and estimation is a prominent
998 challenge with a number of consequences, should it is not addressed appropriately.
999 APSIA methodology can, therefore, be considered as the first step towards not only the
1000 development of a holistic framework that can alleviate this hurdle, but also as the basis
1001 for future research that will attempt to address the following emerging questions.

1002 **Cybersecurity and Privacy Risk Assessment for Supply chains:** As aforemen-
1003 tioned, nowadays, emerging application domains can be seen as “*Systems-of-Systems*”
1004 made up of heterogeneous cyber-physical systems, supplied by multiple vendors, that
1005 are increasingly connected to global information and management networks. Con-
1006 sequently, we must understand such ecosystems as federated safety critical systems
1007 designed, implemented, operated and owned by multiple tenants with different security
1008 and privacy goals, requirements, and priorities. Furthermore, security and privacy
1009 cannot be seen in an isolated way, but must be considered also in the face of the safety of
1010 the overall system. Therefore, it is necessary to understand what is semantically sensible
1011 for a component of a certain type to do and from this microscopic view expand to overall
1012 system analysis. Particularly with respect to security and privacy, components must be
1013 enabled to make and prove statements about their state and actions so that the other
1014 components can align their actions appropriately and an overall system state can be
1015 assessed. This goes substantially beyond simple authorization schemes telling who
1016 may access whom but will require understanding of semantics of requests and chains
1017 of effects throughout the system and an analysis both statically at configuration-time
1018 and dynamically during runtime. The latter will then allow to conduct dynamic risk
1019 assessment and decide at runtime if an entity is still safe to be used; even if some com-
1020 ponents are compromised and fail. Such a reactive, runtime risk assessment model,
1021 facilitating the real-time handling of threats and identified risks, is therefore needed for
1022 conducting a holistic threat assessment of such hyper-connected Systems-of-Systems.
1023 This will enable the dynamic assessment and forecast of individual, cumulative and
1024 propagated risks. Based on the representation of assets along with their dependencies,
1025 the associated threats and vulnerabilities and the potential cascading effects, thus, allow-
1026 ing for enhanced situation awareness adaptation of the entire SoS-enabled ecosystem
1027 supporting policy adjustments and the compilation of updated mitigation strategies.

1028 **Connection between the Physical and Cyber world:** Nowadays, ICT infrastruc-
1029 tures can be seen as complex environments that integrate various technologies and
1030 create a mesh of interconnections among systems, processes and actors. In the con-
1031 text of the well-documented cybersecurity risk assessment field, there is a plethora of
1032 standardised frameworks and guidelines that aim to capture and document the cyber
1033 risks which are triggered as a result of vulnerabilities, attacks and technical flaws that
1034 emerge from the cyber field. In addition, there is a wide spectrum of works that focus
1035 on the analysis of cyber-physical systems, but they revolve around the cyber threats of
1036 those systems [52,53]. Hence, the connection between the two worlds, and the assess-
1037 ment of risks as a result of cascading actions, which are triggered from actors or events
1038 in the physical world and may have an impact to the cyber dimension, is a research
1039 domain with major challenges and room for innovation. Especially when aiming to
1040 privacy preservation, the actions of physical actors (e.g. data processor) could lead to
1041 security incidents that may put data subjects in position to encounter significant, or
1042 even irreversible consequences, which they may not overcome. In this context, there
1043 is an open research question on how to assess, and possibly quantify, those privacy
1044 related cascading risks. Physical-equivalent scoring systems like those developed for the
1045 quantification of the impact of technical vulnerabilities and weaknesses, like CVSS and
1046 CWE would contribute in this direction. In the context of APSIA method and tool, the

interdependency graphs can be used for defining dependencies between the physical and cyber world using the *isUsedBy* and *isLocatedIn* relations. This feature could be used as an enabler for building future methods that consider this connection between the physical and cyber world.

Risk Mitigation through Optimal Countermeasure Selection: In light of the complex and demanding task of risk mitigation, one of the current hurdles that both the scientific community and ICT industry are trying to overcome pertains to the identification of appropriate mitigation actions towards increasing the robustness of cyber defense solutions. In this context, there have been several mechanisms proposed for supporting *automated reaction*; delivering a set of mitigation suggestions to the decision makers [54]. The vast majority of such frameworks capitalise on multi-objective optimisation techniques and constraint solvers in order to find an optimal mitigation action, or a set of actions, that can eliminate the identified risks. More, complex techniques consider game theoretic methods for emulating the engagement between defenders and aggressors [55]. This specific field has a number of challenges to tackle in order to bridge the gap from theory to practice. The scalability of optimisation solutions, in cases where the environment poses several objectives to be met, in conjunction with graph modeling techniques and live feeds of intrusion detection systems [56,57], create wide search areas for the optimal solution and has been reported as a major challenge to overcome. In addition, these optimisation processes do not consider any standard representation of remediation actions or a clear mapping between well-correlated sets of mitigation actions and threats in order to provide interoperable and effective solutions [58]. Notably, the aforementioned endeavors widely neglect the privacy preservation aspect in their objectives. This is mainly due to the fact that cybersecurity and privacy risk assessments are treated as distinct management processes, but also there is a lack of scoring systems that can capture and quantify the interdependence between these two aspects. Therefore, the instantiation of tools like APSIA can enable the model-based risk workflow, scoring and assessment for both the security and privacy assurance of mixed-criticality applications. Risks that have been identified in core assets (comprising the target application), can be weighted according to their criticality and impact degree, allowing the resolution of an optimization problem for the selection, deployment and placement of the best set of possible mitigation actions; ranging from the enactment of security solutions based on traditional cryptographic primitives (i.e., symmetric/asymmetric encryption, digital signatures [59], etc.) to more advanced trust assurance services [60,61] including network-based intrusion detection systems or (remote) attestation controls. However, despite the clear benefits of such approaches, their applicability in environments with resource constrained devices, especially when it comes to privacy-related mitigation actions, is rather challenging [62].

For instance, strong cryptographic protocols can be used to increase trust, by not letting privacy risks be technically possible. Over the past years, a number of technologies have been developed to build Privacy Preserving Attribute-based Credentials (Privacy-ABCs) in a way that they can be trusted, like normal cryptographic certificates, while at the same time they protect the privacy of their holder [63]. Such Privacy-ABCs are issued just like ordinary cryptographic credentials using a digital secret signature key [59]. However, Privacy-ABCs allow their holder to transform them into a new token, in such a way that the privacy of the user is protected [64]. Bringing more control on the edge side, however, also gave birth to Direct Anonymous Attestation [65,66]; a platform authentication mechanism that enables the provision of privacy-preserving and accountable services. DAA is based on group signatures that allow remote attestation of a device associated to a Trusted Component (TC) while offering strong anonymity guarantees. Standardised by the Trusted Computing Group (TCG), DAA retains user anonymity, provides device-controlled unlinkability, and identifies signatures created by compromised devices. Given the aforementioned challenges, the privacy scoring system

Table 6: Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
APS	Asset-level Privacy Score
APSA	Automated Privacy & Security Impact Assessment
BPM LCM	Business Process Model Life-Cycle Management
CISO	Chief Information Security Officer
CPS	Cyber Physical Systems
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CVSS	Common Vulnerability Scoring System
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIS	Health Information System
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MC	Mitigation Controls
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NVD	National Vulnerability Database
OPS	Organisation-level Privacy Score
PAPS	Processing Activity-level Privacy Score
PET	Privacy-Enhancing Technologies
PIA	Privacy Impact Assessment
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
pISRA	Privacy-considered Information Security Risk Assessment
POC	Point of Care
RMF	Risk Management Framework
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SPIA	Security and Privacy Impact Assessment
SSN	Social Security Number

1100 and methodology of APSIA could be used as an enabler for building such decision
1101 support systems that focus to the privacy realm.

1102 7. Conclusion

1103 In this work, we presented the APSIA methodology and tool in order to bridge the
1104 gap between the (automated) cybersecurity and privacy risk assessment conduction,
1105 which are widely treated as distinct management processes. The building blocks of
1106 APSIA, namely the *Interdependency Graphs*, the *Privacy Scoring System*, and the *Data*
1107 *processing flows modeling based on GDPR* are unified under the umbrella of an assessment
1108 methodology that enables the automated risk identification from data flows, the au-
1109 tomatic creation of PIA reports, and the continuous execution of the risk assessment
1110 steps. The aforementioned offerings, were evaluated in the context of a heavily regulated
1111 sector (namely, the assistive healthcare domain) where strict security and privacy con-
1112 siderations are not only expected but mandated so as to better showcase the beneficial
1113 characteristics of APSIA. More specifically, the interdependency graphs were used to
1114 generate a detailed cartography of the engaged assets in the data processing activities
1115 of an emulated healthcare network. Based on this view, APSIA generated a number of
1116 flows that revealed the manner and under what conditions patients' sensitive data
1117 are handled in the organisation. Crucially, the identified cyber security vulnerabilities of
1118 the core infrastructure assets were evaluated based on the novel privacy scoring system,
1119 in order to acquire a quantification of the impact of the vulnerability in the privacy
1120 dimension. This privacy-oriented score steers the decision maker in identifying, priori-
1121 tising, anticipating and, finally, mitigating the risks by having privacy as the prominent
1122 quality that needs to be safeguarded.

1123 Overall, all these APSIA innovations enable the presented tool to exceed the rigid
1124 approaches of privacy impact assessment and provide the means to conduct an *en-*
1125 *hanced, dynamic* and *generic* assessment as an integral part of an iterative and unified

1126 risk assessment process on-the-fly. In this context, while one could argue that APSIA
1127 is limited only to the GDPR-related privacy considerations, the core methodology is
1128 generic enough to facilitate any ecosystem with “privacy-by-design” properties. Since
1129 such properties are independent of the system or the application domain itself, putting
1130 forth the methodology to be able to precisely model them in the presence of strong
1131 adversaries is a prerequisite for any legal framework. Given this remark, however,
1132 we aim to extend APSIA and evaluate it in scenarios with privacy principles that are
1133 documented by additional legal frameworks (i.e NIST). Furthermore, as a future work,
1134 we aim to deploy and evaluate APSIA in a larger pilot and perform improvements on
1135 the usability of the tool according to the views of engaged stakeholders.

1136 Finally, by taking into consideration the salient characteristics of risk assessment,
1137 as a building block, along with the requirements of the involved actors, we identified
1138 a number of open research challenges. It is our strong belief that if these challenges
1139 are tackled now while APSIA is still at an early stage, then, this emerging security and
1140 privacy mechanism can reach its full potential.

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Appendix A APSIA Graphical User Interface components

Figure A2. Patient Registration Risk Data Flows

Figure A1. Data processing flows in the frame of GDPR

Figure A3. Patient Monitoring Risk Data Flows

Figure A4. APSIA Dashboard heat-maps and histograms